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Constraints in Stem Cuttings Propagation of Faloak (*Sterculia quadrifida* R.Br.) in High Temperature Region

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ABSTRACT

The bark of faloak is used for treating liver diseases while the wood is used in house constructions. Seed exploration in several islands is constrained by the least number of trees and only few trees produce fruits. The purpose of this study was to investigate the factors that causing low survival rate of faloak stem cuttings in Kupang. The method used in this study is a combination of the length of cuttings (9, 18 and 27cm) and rooting medium (soil, soil + manure, soil + sand, sand and cocopeat). The results showed that the survival rate of stem cuttings is very low, the highest survival rate was found in 27cm length of cuttings with medium of rooting is soil (100%) and cocopeat (100%). High temperatures and low humidity in the nursery may become the limiting factors in vegetative propagation of faloak and causing low survival rate of the stem cuttings.

Keywords: faloak, *Sterculia quadrifida*, climate, semi arid, shoots.

1. INTRODUCTION

Plants can be propagated in vegetative or generative ways. Vegetative propagation uses several parts of the plant for reproducing the plant asexually. Vegetative propagation is usually aimed at genetic preservation of a plant because this method can produce offspring that has identical genetic properties. Moreover, vegetative propagation method can overcome some problems of plant propagation such as infertile plants, limited availability of seeds, and slow growth plants. Stem cuttings are the most common method used of vegetative propagation. Factors affecting stem cuttings are cuttings material, environmental factors such as temperature, and cuttings preparation technique (Arifin *et al.*, 2015).

Land in East Nusa Tenggara (NTT) consists mostly of rocks with thin soil solum. Timor Island has a semi-arid climate with low-rainfall causing difficulty for some plant species to breed naturally. Plants in high-temperature regions are more sensitive to the increasing of air temperature (Zhang *et al.*, 2015). Faloak (*Sterculia quadrifida* R. Br.) from family Sterculiaceae is a species that widely use as medicinal plant in Timor Island. Its bark is mainly used to treat liver disease (Siswadi *et al.*, 2015). Faloak grows naturally and spreads over several regencies in Timor Island although it is not distributed evenly (Siswadi *et al.*, 2013). Faloak has orthodox seeds and generally could be dried to low moisture content, however harsh environment causes faloak seeds difficult to germinate. Faloak trees are not distributed evenly in a population and many faloak trees do not produce fruits annually. These are obstacles in generative propagation of faloak and its genetic conservation. Vegetative propagation using stem cuttings is expected to overcome these obstacles. This research

is aimed to investigate the factors that may causing low survival rate of faloak stem cuttings in Kupang.

2. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1 Time and Location

This research was conducted in May to August 2016 in Kupang (10°10'49.94"S, 123°35'25.60"E) East Nusa Tenggara (NTT) Province.

2.2 Materials and Tools

Materials used in this study included: faloak stems, polybag, sand, soil, manure, cocopeat, paranet (60%), fungicide, clear plastic bag, small wooden sticks, wire, water and Atonik AL (5% solution). Tools used in data collection were digital caliper, sharp knife, pruning shears, termohygrometer, ruler, pH meter, and digital camera.

2.3 Methods

Procedure:

- Select and cut stems from vigorous faloak trees using a sharp clean knife or pruning shears. Stem cuttings should not be taken from plant source that showing symptoms of diseases and damages from insects (Hutasoit *et al.*, 2013). Stems were cut in three different lengths (9, 18 and 27 cm long).
- Before plant the stems in rooting medium, stem cuttings were soaked in Atonik solution for 30 minute.
- There were 5 rooting medium used in this study: soil [100%], soil+manure [50:50], soil+sand [50:50], sand [100%] and cocopeat [100%]. There were 30 replications for each combination of stem cuttings length and rooting medium. A total of 450 stem cuttings were observed.
- Stem cuttings were planted in a plastic container and kept in propagation tunnel made of wooden sticks structure and covered with clear plastic. This plastic tunnel is aimed to maintain the temperature and humidity. The plastic then covered with paranet to reduce the intensity of sunlight. The stem cuttings were watered every alternate day and maintained for ten weeks. Temperatures and humidity in the inside the propagation tunnel and environment outside the tunnel were recorded daily with a thermohygrometer.

2.4 Data Analysis

Data collected in this study were the number of rooting stem cuttings, daily temperature and humidity. The data collected were tabulated and used to calculate mortality rate, rooting percentage of faloak stem cuttings, as well as average temperature and humidity.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of 450 faloak cuttings were placed under a plastic tunnel to maintain the temperature and humidity (Figure 1). In the second week, most of cuttings showed relatively good growth. It is indicated by new leaves growth (Figure 2). However, in the fourth week, some of the stem cuttings were began to shrivel.

Figure 1: Stem cuttings and rooting medium preparation.

Figure 2: Stem cuttings began to grow leaves in the 2nd week.

Cuttings were growing some leaves but not showing signs of rooting (Figure 3). Started in the fourth week the survival rates were decreasing continuously (Figure 4).

Figure 3: A 2 week old stem cutting with new leaves but no sign of rooting

Figure 4: Weekly survival rates of faloak stem cuttings were decreasing.

Table 1: Faloak stem cuttings survival rate in week 10.

Cuttings media	Survival rate [%]		
	Cuttings length [cm]		
	9	18	27
Soil+Manure	-	3,3	3,3
Soil+Sand	-	-	3,3
Soil	-	3,3	6,7
Sand	-	3,3	-
Cocopeat	-	3,3	6,7

In the end of the 10th week, only cuttings with the length of 18 & 27 cm having roots with very low survival rate (Table 1). None of the 9 cm length of stem cuttings rooted. In this study, vegetative propagation of faloak showed very low percentage of survival rate. Physiological, biochemistry, and environmental factors may causing unsuccessful vegetative propagation. Some plant species

are difficult to propagated using vegetative methods, for example *Azadirachta indica* (Sharma *et al.*, 2016). Faloak may have certain traits that cause difficulties to be cultivated by vegetative propagation. Problems such as the right maturity of cuttings and rooting issues are constraints in vegetative propagation of some species. Moreover, environmental factors such as high temperature and low humidity often become limiting factors in vegetative propagation. In some cases, the types of rooting medium also affect the success of vegetative propagation.

The plastic tunnel was aimed to protect the cuttings from direct sunlight. By using the shaded cover, the humidity and temperature were expected to be maintained in stable condition and suitable to induce rooting. However, Kupang has a natural high average temperature and low humidity. Based on the temperature and humidity data of Kupang area from the Indonesian Agency for Meteorology, Climatology and Geophysics (BMKG) of Kupang, during June to July 2016 the average daily temperature in Kupang was 26,5°C. The highest temperature was in May 2016 which reached 32,2°C. Meanwhile, the average humidity in Kupang in 2016 was 76% and the lowest humidity was in July (71%) (Badan Metereologi Klimatologi dan Geofisika Kupang, 2017).

The highest temperature inside the propagation tunnel was 30,8 °C. During rooting initiation, the ideal temperature for plants is 21°-27° or 29°C (Djamhuri, 2011). Such high temperature and low humidity stimulate the stems to form buds but not induce rooting. In this initiation period cuttings used energy in the stem to grow shoots and leaves. Meanwhile, the absence of the root causes the nutrient supply from the root by the xylem tissue cannot be transported to the leaves so that the assimilation process cannot take place. The ideal temperature of rooting medium to be able to induce roots cells division is below 24°C (Rochiman dan Harjadi, 1973). The average humidity recorded in the propagation tunnel was 84,25%, meanwhile the lowest humidity was 72%. According to Djamhuri (2011), the optimum humidity to induce rooting of stem cuttings is 90%. High humidity is crucial for cuttings growth to inhibit transpiration, preventing cuttings from shrivelled before rooting. Humidity level which is lower than 90% was considered inadequate and can cause cuttings mortality (Rochiman dan Harjadi, 1973). Low humidity and high temperature are increasing transpiration and causing *kayu kuku* (*Pericopsis mooniana* THW) cuttings to dry out (Sukendro & Putri, 2016). In contrary, Prihatin's (2000) experiment on stem cuttings of Nitas (*Sterculia foetida*) recorded 48% of survival rate. Cuttings were maintained in temperature below 25°C and humidity higher than 85%. This study was conducted in Bogor which has lower daily temperature and higher humidity compared to Kupang.

According to Tombesi *et al.* (2015) to be able to form roots, cuttings require energy which obtained from carbohydrates that have been stored in the tissue of the cuttings. Cuttings with higher carbohydrates are more easily rooted than cuttings with low carbohydrates. The mortality of faloak cuttings is marked by discoloration of leaves and buds. Whitish colour of the leaves and buds are signs that the plant is not able to form chlorophyll due to unavailability of roots. In addition, as temperatures increase, the rate of transpiration increases is higher than the rate of increase of photosynthesis (Zhang *et al.*, 2009).

As shown in Table 1, the percentage of rooted cuttings was very low, particularly cuttings of 9 cm long. Stem cuttings of 18 and 27 cm long has a higher survival rate compared with 9 cm cuttings. It can be infer that the longer the length of the cuttings, the higher chance of cuttings to survive. According to Arifin *et al.*, (2015) cuttings with a length of 30 cm and addition of organic fertilizer in the rooting medium showed the best results compared with cuttings of 20 and 25 cm long and planted in medium without addition of organic fertilizer. Rooting media with high survival rate of cuttings were soil and cocopeat. Cocopeat has low nutrients content (Suryawan, 2014) but it can bind and store water very well (Irawan & Hidayah, 2014).

4. CONCLUSIONS

The major constraints of faloak vegetative propagation in Kupang were high temperature and low humidity. Propagation tunnel construction and regular watering were not able to maintain temperature and humidity that suitable for rooting. It was affected by the high temperature and low humidity environment in Kupang. More research is needed to investigate the presence of physiological and biochemistry factors that may also affect the survival rate of faloak stem cuttings.

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**"Promoting Sustainable Resources
from Plantations for Economic Growth and
Community Benefits"**

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Research Development and Innovation Agency

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PREFACE

In a global scale, planted forest areas continue to increase, and that the goods and services provided by these forests are becoming increasingly diverse. The interaction of planted forests with other land uses within landscapes and their contribution to poverty alleviation and food security is complex. Risks to planted forests from climate change, socio-economic pressures and responses to these risks have been the subjects of studies. The importance of planted forests for economic, environmental and social values have been globally recognized.

For the past 30 years, acacias and eucalypts have been two of the major forest plantation species of choice in the tropics, particularly in South-East Asia. Selected acacia species have high rates of growth, are tolerant of acidic, low nutrient and degraded soils, and in Indonesia have been easy to establish in landscapes dominated by *Imperata* grassland. Harvested plantation acacias are now an important global resource with >3.5M ha grown in Asia, Africa and South America. They supply fibre for pulp and paper industries, wood for furniture, building materials, and charcoal and other fuels, as well as being used for the protection of water catchments.

After several successive and successful rotations, growers are now facing various challenges that threaten the sustainability of acacia pulpwood plantations. Pests and diseases, soil compaction, weed invasiveness and a changing climate have become major topics of interest to researchers working with plantation growers to seek ways of confronting and adapting to these challenges. In recent years growers have replaced acacias with eucalypts, particularly *E. pellita*.

At this difficult time for plantation growers in the tropics, IUFRO Working Party 2.08.07 (Genetics and Silviculture of Acacias) in collaboration with FOERDIA INAFOR IV organised a Joint International Conference on 24-27 July 2017 in Jogjakarta, Indonesia. The Conference had adopted a theme "**Promoting Sustainable Resources from Plantations for Economic Growth and Community Benefits**", that reflects the challenges being confronted by plantations. It brought together researchers, plantation managers and policy makers from around the world for an intensive four days of exchanging views, present their latest findings, build a networking.

Papers and posters presented in the IUFRO-INAFOR conference are compiled into proceeding. This proceeding is a documentation and publication of papers and posters presented during the conference. It consists of 84 papers from 25 of presented papers and 59 presented posters. We hope this proceedings could be distributed to all participants, users, partners and other stakeholders for their references.

In this opportunity, on behalf of Forestry and Environment Research, Development and Innovation Agency (FOERDIA) I would like to thank to all the authors of papers and posters contributed in this proceedings. The critical comments and reviews from the editors are also appreciated. I am also grateful for the participants who had actively involved and the committee who have been working hard to host the conference successfully. Finally, I wish this proceeding could contribute the benefits to the society in strengthening forest science and technology towards sustainable forest management and community welfare.

Bogor, Agustus 2018

Director General

Dr. Agus Justianto

Previous Proceedings International Conference of Indonesia Forestry Researchers (INAFOR)

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I	2011	Bogor	Forestry Research and Development Agency	978-979-8452-45-1
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